

Empowerment of women- myths and reality

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Introduction

“Being a woman should be your supreme achievement and not your deepest fear. Celebrate womanhood, fuel yourself with self-confidence and let that fuel empower you to soar towards your dream” – **Mani Mukhija**. Very rightly said these lines of mani mukhija inspires each and every woman to be proud of their womanhood and not let it become your fear to be a woman but as we see in today’s era, almost everyone is in favor of women empowerment but only very few are there who actually know the meaning of women empowerment. Women empowerment is something where each and every female gets equal rights, opportunities, respect, love, status and power in the same way males get in society. I don’t mean that only males are getting opportunities in this era, women are also provided with many opportunities but not every woman is able to enjoy those opportunities or liberties. But some people have made this world to be a place of frightening for females. Some girls who want to do something in their life are not allowed by the family to do so and they are forced to early marriage, some females who are working and living their life independently are harassed in their job places due to which their level of confidence goes on decreasing and they are indirectly forced to better leave that place and be at home itself, some girls are not even able to see the world as they are killed inside their mother’s womb, especially in India this killing of girl child is practiced in many areas and then comes one of the most disheartening thing that is happening nowadays, rape. So many cases are there in India where even the infant girls are raped and due to this fear, those girls never uplift themselves in the society because the people nearby see them with a view that they can be nothing in their life. Instead of so many rules and regulations made for the upliftment of women they are not getting empowered due to reasons stated above. In order to resolve these issues certain strict measures should be taken by the government, so that if anyone tries to do such type of practice with any female, he/she must get severe punishment, due to which others may get a lesson and instead of blaming the women for their fate, the guilty ones must suffer and each and every woman may live their life with head always uplifted and confident.

Meaning of women empowerment

Empowerment can be basically seen as the ability of an individual to make decisions individually or collectively in society. Empowerment means people who are empowered to decide, think or act freely in any situation, use their choice and fully fulfill their potential as equal members of the society. The empowerment of women is critical to the development of a society or nation. According to United Nations Women's Development Fund (UNIFEM), the term women empowerment means¹:

- Gaining knowledge and understanding of sexual relationships and the ways in which these relationships can be changed.
- Creating a sense of self-worth, a belief in one's ability to make the changes he or she wants the right to control one's life.
- Gaining the power to make the power of negotiation use choice.
- To develop the ability to plan and influence the direction of social change, to create good social and economic order, nationally and internationally.

Empowerment of women- Indian aspect

India is very well known for its culture and heritage since ancient times. But on the other hand it is also know very well for its male dominant society across the world. Women are given priority in India but they are exploited in the family and society through violence, mistreat, etc. They are limited to do household work, take care of the family and children only. Very few women are allowed to do work after their marriage and some are not even allowed to go out and do job before marriage also. The women in many areas across India are kept unaware of their rights and development. Although the constitution of India is a legitimate point to provide each and every women with equality in all spheres of society like men. The department of Women and Children development is working well in the field to develop women and children in a better way. Empowering women is the main motto of this department because an empowered mother with a child creates a bright future for any nation.

¹ <http://www.legalservicesindia.com/article/1955/Women-empowerment:-With-Special-Reference-to-Constitutional-Provisions.html>

By providing Social equality and justice for women, the best measure that has been taken by the government is the integration of other personal laws in our country. In the area of justice, gender neutrality has served for the suffering of accused female because in some cases it burdened the prosecutor, e.g. in cases of rape. These examples of gender inequality or discrimination were fought against the judiciary and were added into binding of rules for provision of social equality and justice in disadvantaged sectors or areas. The constitution of India has passed some amendments which shows equal political rights of women as men and these include the demand for 33% seats in lok sabha and vidhan sabhas. The empowerment of women in politics has been amended by 73 and 744 amendments to women seats in gram panchayats and municipal policies.

Constitutional provisions relating to equality

Part III of the constitution containing Article 12-35 is the heart of Indian Constitution which deals with the Fundamental rights. These are: Right to equality, including equality in front of Law, prohibition of discrimination on grounds of race, caste, sex, religion or place of birth and also contains equality in matters of opportunity for employment.

These Fundamental rights were added in the Indian constitution because these were considered to be essential for the personality development of each and every individual and to preserve human dignity.

Article 14 (Equality before Law)

According to this article, *the state shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India.*²

Article 15 (Prohibition of discrimination on grounds of sex, race, religion, caste, place of birth)

- 1) *The state shall not discriminate against any citizen of country on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth or any of the above.*
- 2) *No citizen shall, on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth or any of them, be subject to any disability, liability, restriction or condition regarding-*
 - a) access to shops, public restaurants, hotels or places of public entertainment; or

² <https://www.clearias.com/fundamental-rights/>

b) the use of wells, tanks, roads, bathing ghats and places of public resort maintained wholly or partially out of the state funds or dedicated to the use of general public.

3) *Nothing in this article shall prevent the state from forming any special provisions for children and women.*³

Article 16(Equality of opportunity in matters of public employment)

1) *There shall be equality of opportunity for all citizens in matters relating to employment or appointment to any office under the state.*

2) *No citizen shall, on grounds of religion, caste, sex, race, descent, place of birth, residence or any these, be ineligible for, or discriminated against in respect of, any employment or office under the state.*

3) *Nothing in this article shall prevent parliament from making any law prescribing, in regarding to any class or classes of employment or the appointment to an office.*

Conclusion

The most important part with which women empowerment could increase is education because the literacy rate in India is not much and because of which most the women are totally unaware of their rights, which the constitution provides them with. So if all the women in India would be educated than they'll be able to fight for their violated rights. It will also lead to improved economic growth and also the level of participation in politics would increase with women's education because women with lower education rates are pushed into less productive fields like labour jobs, household care job, etc. Illiteracy, economic dependence, physical violence and political ignorance are some the factors that prevent women from enhancing their power in the country. The government of India should better work in these fields to encourage more participation of women and also keep a check on different sectors whether the functioning of them is done indiscriminately or not. If such serious steps will be taken by the government then only the exploitation of women will become less and they'll be able to enjoy their rights equally as men.

³ <https://www.clearias.com/fundamental-rights/>